

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7978834

QUANTIFYING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY VIA PULSOMETRY IN 10-13-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN'S NON-FORMAL PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN SCHOOL

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Abstract

Objectives. The aim of the present study was to determine for quantifying the non-formal physical education settings time that 10-13 years children spent in moderate to vigorous physical activity.

Methods. Data were collected during PA project "Move and Know" (NR. SRF-FAV-2022-1-0096) in the 2022–2023 academic year. Participants were 130 (68 girls, 62 boys) elementary school children aged between 10 to 13 years ($M = 11.55 \pm .88$ years) recruited from eight Klaipeda city public schools. The sample included 52.3% girls. 37.3% of 10–13-year-old children participated in sports, i.e., attended NFPE at school or out of school. Pulsometers (Polar Pacer) and Polar Team Pro App were used to objectively collect Heart Rate (HR) data.

Results. The children's mean heart rate was 135.01 ± 16.90 bpm, and the maximum heart rate was 174.98 ± 18.25 bpm. The duration of activities was 59.11 ± 5.30 min. Analysis of the load distribution by intensity zones revealed that the biggest part of NFPE time children spent in Zone 1, Zone 2, and Zone 3. The results showed that girls ($M = 23.67$, $SD = 16.15$) spend more PA time in Zone 1 than boys ($M = 19.13$, $SD = 13.57$).

Conclusion. The intensity of non-formal physical education met the recommendations - more than 50% of physical activity during NFPE was from moderate to vigorous intensity. Based on these data, it is clear that non-formal physical education, during which innovative technologies are used, significantly contributes to the implementation of recommendations for children's physical activity.

Keywords: physical activity, children, heart rate, pulsometer

Introduction. Evidence-based research increasingly suggests that various forms and doses of physical activity (PA) are effective in combating many chronic diseases, improving wellbeing and mental health [5]. Physical activity provides us with a variety of health benefits which depend upon the duration, frequency, intensity, and type of exercise. The intensity of exercise is the most elusive of these elements and yet has important implications for the health benefits and particularly cardiovascular outcomes elicited by regular physical activity. World Health Organisation [6] guidelines state that achieving an average of 60 min per day of moderate-to-vigorous intensity physical activity (MVPA) provides children with a wide variety of health benefits.

Unfortunately, most children and adolescents globally have low levels of MVPA and do not meet the previous WHO recommendations (i.e., achieving at least 60 min MVPA daily). The Health Behaviour in School-aged Children study [3] reported that only 24% of 11-year-old children and 19% of 13-year-old children are meeting the recommended physical activity - at least 60 minutes of MVPA daily.

Youth physical activity behaviours are influenced by many sectors of society, including families, community organizations, health care providers, faith-based institutions, government agencies, the media, and schools. All these sectors should be involved to increase youth physical activity. However, schools play an especially important role. Childhood obesity: a plan for action [2] set out that children and young people should achieve the recommended 60 minutes of physical activity daily through 30 minutes during the school day and 30 minutes outside of school. According to the recommendations of the Association for Physical Education [1] students should spend 50–80% of their physical education time in moderate-to-vigorous intensity.

Mears, R., Jago, R. [4], who conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis claim that despite many studies nevertheless more robust evaluations of NFPE interventions are required, particularly studies that use objective assessment of physical activity.

The aim of the present study was to determine for quantifying the non-formal physical education settings time that 10-13 years children spent in moderate to vigorous physical activity.

Material and Methods. Data were collected in the framework of the project “Move and Know” (NR. SRF-FAV-2022-1-0096) during the 2022–2023 academic year. Each Klaipeda city (Lithuania) public schools received a written invitation to participate, together with general information about project. With the school’s principals, that decided to participate in the project, an agreement for participation in the project was signed. A schedule of activities was created. NFPE were organized at the end of formal education. Children used to come to the Klaipeda University sport hall, where an “i Sport Wall” was installed and NFPE was held.

Participants were 130 (68 girls, 62 boys) elementary school children aged between 10 to 13 years ($M = 11.55 \pm .88$ years) recruited from eight Klaipeda city public schools. Information on nationality, age, sex, height, weight and participation in NFPE were collected. 96.2% were Lithuanian citizens, 3.8% citizens of Ukraine. The sample included 52.3% girls. 37.3% of 10–13-year-old children participated in sports, i.e., attended NFPE at school or out of school. During height and weight measurements participants had bare feet and wore light underclothes. Height was measured to the nearest 1 mm and weight to the nearest 0.05 kg using a standard beam balance with a stadiometer (SECA 709; Germany).

Pulsometers (Polar Pacer) and Polar Team Pro App were used to objectively collect Heart Rate (HR) data. This technology enables real-time tracking of HR (in 5-s intervals) of each student. The polar Team Pro App allowed the extraction of the following variables during each NFPE: minimum HR, average HR, maximum HR, calories burned, total sensor wear time, and time at each HR zone (i.e., very light (50–60%), light (60–70%), moderate (70–80%), hard (80–90%), very hard (90–100%)). In our study, MVPA is considered from Zone 2 to Zone 5.

Before starting the research, a profile of each student was created with the Polar Team Pro App, including information about age, gender, height, and weight. All children wore a heart rate monitor during the NFPE. Data recording began when the teachers would officially start the activity and stopped at the end.

Descriptive statistics data are presented as means (M) and standard deviations (SD). Independent t test and Mann-Whitney U test were used to examine test differences between two

independent groups. Analyses were performed with the IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 26.0. A p value < 0.05 denoted statistical significance.

Results. Descriptive characteristics of the study sample (age, weight, height and duration of participating in NFPE) for boys, girls and all participants are presented in Table 1 as means and standard deviations.

Table 1. Participants' characteristics

Characteristics		Boys (n=62) Mean (SD)	Girls (n=68) Mean (SD)	All (n=130) Mean (SD)
Age (years)		11.26 (.68)*	11.82 (.96)	11.55 (0.88)
Weight (kg)		39.417 (8.22)*	43.48 (9.83)	38.93 (13.44)
Height (cm)		147.63 (7.47)*	152.03 (8.60)	140.64 (37.04)
Participating in NFPE		58.1*	19.1	37.7
Duration of participating in NFPE	Less than 1 year	24,2	8,8	16.2
	1-2 years	11,3	1,5	6.2
	3-4 years	6,5	5,9	6.2
	More than 4 years	12,9	2,9	7.7

* significantly different from girls (p < 0.05)

The children' mean heart rate was 135.01 ± 16.90 bpm, and the maximum heart rate was 174.98 ± 18.25 bpm. Duration of activities was 59.11±5.30 min. Analysis of the load distribution by intensity zones revealed that the biggest part of NFPE time children spent in Zone 1, Zone 2, and Zone 3. Average HR, maximum HR and percentage of time spent in different physical activity zones are described in table 2. HR results differences between children who participate in NFPE and don't participate were not significant, p>0.05.

Table 2. Heart rate values in relation to the student's gender

	Boys (n=62) Mean (SD)	Girls (n=68) Mean (SD)	All (n=130) Mean (SD)
HR_average	136,70 (16.00)	133,46 (17.66)	135,01 (16.90)
HR_average (%)	65,41 (7.64)	63,88 (8.46)	64,62 (8.09)
HR_max	176,24 (17.82)	173,82 (16.69)	174,98 (18.25)
HR_max (%)	83,66(10.31)	82,90 (9.24)	83,26 (9.73)
Zone 1 (%)	32,37 (22.96)	41,18 (28.60)	36,95 (26.33)
Zone 2 (%)	32,90 (13.20)	28,49 (13.85)	30,59 (13.67)
Zone 3 (%)	23,52 (15.38)	19,51 (16.02)	21,42 (15.79)
Zone 4 (%)	9,86 (12.60)	8,97 (11.81)	9,39 (12.15)
Zone 5 (%)	1,26 (2.86)	1,63 (5.11)	1,45 (4.19)

Figure 1 shows the results of time spent in different physical activity zones. An independent-samples t-test was run to determine gender differences. The results showed that girls ($M = 23.67$, $SD = 16.15$) spend more PA time in Zone 1 than boys ($M = 19.13$, $SD = 13.57$).

This difference was significant $t(128) = -1.729$, $p < 0.05$. Other differences were not significant, $p > 0.05$.

Figure 1. Time spent in different physical activity intensity zones

Conclusion. The intensity of non-formal physical education met the recommendations - more than 50% of physical activity during NFPE was from moderate to vigorous intensity. Based on these data, it is clear that non-formal physical education, during which innovative technologies are used, significantly contributes to the implementation of recommendations for children's physical activity.

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